

Exploring The Factors and Effect of Sustainable Reverse Logistic Capabilities...

Exploring The Factors and Effect of Sustainable Reverse Logistic Capabilities in The Petrochemical Industry of Pakistan

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of sustainable reverse logistics capabilities on the petrochemical industry in Pakistan. It showed that the degree to which organizations are committed to sustainable supply chain management affects the level of commitment to sustainable reverse logistics and subsequent operational performance. The findings revealed that sustainable reverse logistics capabilities have a significant mediating effect on the relationship between commitment to sustainability and operational performance within the petrochemical industry in Pakistan. Sustainable reverse logistics capabilities help increase the benefits of the commitment to sustainability and enhance the performance of the industry overall. By increasing their commitment to sustainability, organizations within the petrochemical industry of Pakistan can benefit from the positive effect of sustainable reverse logistics capabilities and consequently improve their operational performance. The findings indicate that organizations engaged in sustainable supply chain management must be aware of the importance of sustainable reverse logistics capabilities and take appropriate steps to maximize efficiencies during the reverse logistics process. This study provides guidelines that would enable petrochemical firms to become more environmentally conscious which may result in improved performance. However, it should be noted that the scope of the study was limited due to geographical and technological constraints, as well as restrictions in the sample size, and may not be generalizable to other industries.

Keywords: Sustainable Reverse Logistics, Petrochemical Industry, Pakistan

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1. INTRODUCTION

Research has focused on developing effective supply chain management (SCM) tools to give organizations or firms a competitive advantage (Christopher and Towill, 2001). The aim of SCM is to optimize the utilization of assets and other processes along the supply chain. With the rise of technological advancements, the business world has become increasingly unpredictable. This shift has led to an increasing number of ecological changes in recent years (Sarkis, 2001). The Brundtland report (1987) entitled “Our Common Future” sparked a renewed interest in sustainability and the green environment. Researchers studied sustainable supply chains through case studies, articles, modeling, literature and other methods (Winter and Knemeyer, 2013). The link between the implementation of reverse logistics activities and sustainability is still not clear.

It has been proposed that incorporating reverse logistics practices could be a component of a comprehensive sustainable SCM strategy (Ansari and Qureshi, 2015). “A number of studies have been conducted to explore the sustainability issues inherent in existing SCM and logistics paradigms (Sarkis et al., 2010; Stock et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2017)”. Many companies are introducing innovative reverse logistics (RL) initiatives to enhance their ecological and financial performance (Huang and Yang, 2014). If appropriately managed, reverse logistics can help improve the overall efficiency of the supply chain (Khan & Subzwari, 2009). High levels of SCM have been correlated with improved organizational performance (Li et al., 2006).

In Pakistan, businesses traditionally prioritize profit over all else, with their supply chain strategies only focusing on forward logistics. However, changing global affairs and recent research have encouraged companies to reconsider their stakeholders’ approaches, shifting to embrace environmental sustainability even in their supply chain strategies. A successful plan includes investments in reverse logistics, which helps the firm recover a product after its useful life ends. This puts emphasis on the “triple bottom line” profitability: financial gain, social responsibility, and environmental impact (Sarwar & Ahmed, 2011).

The petrochemical industry is leading the way when it comes to incorporating sustainable supply chain operations and reverse logistics. Refurbishment and replenishment can recover a great deal of the product's value; up to 70-80%. Incorporating sustainability into their routines bear an additional cost - from recovery to program implementation (Douglas, 2016) - creating a financial burden for these organizations. It is thus critical for researchers and organizations to understand the interconnections between sustainable supply chain and reverse logistics, and how these affect operational performance.

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Organisations move towards sustainability is an extremely important aspect in the present business environment due to the rapid changes and increasing demands for sustainability. To ensure profitable businesses, companies have been focusing on introducing preemptive strategies and tactics in order to strengthen their competencies and skills. To improve operational performance, this study analyses the relationship between commitment to sustainability of reverse logistics and supply chain management. The important purpose of this research is to present clear-cut recommendations to organisations in order to develop ecological reverse logistics strategies with both short-term and long-term sustainable effects, making it a robust strategy and a substantial operational undertaking (Reuter et al., 2010). Reverse logistics is acknowledged as one of the important parts of supply chain management as it focuses on customer returns, salvaging of products and its residual values. As for these reasons, it has been recognized as a necessary component of transportation, production and storage activities for the sustainability of an organisation (Wong et al., 2017). Strategic use of reverse logistics systems can increase operational performance significantly and improve the capability to achieve an acceptable rate of return (Le et al., 2020). With the right strategies and implementations, reverse logistics can maximise value of products, reduce operational costs and transport costs as well as minimise environmental footprints (Saadatersesht et al., 2020).

By understanding the impact of sustainable reverse logistic capabilities on operational performance, organisations can develop strategies needed to maximise efficiency and effectiveness so as to improve their customer services, reduce cost, as well as increase profitability while maintaining sustainable operations. The research seeks to provide recommendations to corporations and businesses in order to yield more profitable and sustainable outcomes from their reverse logistic strategies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Commitment to SSCM:

Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) is an approach dedicated to achieving environmental sustainability. According to Gupta, S., and Palsule-Desai (2011), this system incorporates three main principles: consideration of ecological impacts, assessment of the full production cycle and evaluation of the product's life span from its extraction to its final use. The environment has been suffering due to the rapid depletion of resources, green house emissions, toxic waste etc., leading to an alarming rise in global temperatures (Walker et al., 2008). This, in turn, is leading the government, companies, customers, suppliers, and individuals towards sustainability.

Carter and Rogers (2008) are accredited with the creation of a framework of Sustainable Supply Chain Management which revolves around resource management. It is necessary for the organization to make sure that its employees are engaging in sustainable practices through trainings, workshops and spreading awareness. Through such activities, it will be possible to achieve sustainability through balancing the profit, environment, culture, and community of the organization (Rezaee, 2018).

SSCM is required for bringing about a change in the supply chain processes by making sure that enough consideration is given for the environmental concern if reversing or for worrying

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in the forward direction (Rao and Holt, 2005). For instance, upstream sustainable supply chain management helps in monitoring the activities of suppliers, i.e. reducing wasted activities or non-lean activities. On the other side, downstream SSCM focuses on the product usage and disposal (Geyer and Jackson, 2004).

Every organization should strive towards SSCM in order to gain competitive advantage and reduce the utilization of resources. Achieving the best SSCM process requires working closely with suppliers, customers, business owners and other managers for coordination among these systems (Kozma, 2017 & 'Slusarczyk, 2017). Furthermore, it is also necessary for the organization to clearly define the sustainability goals as well as involve the employees by providing them workshops and training sessions (Closs et al., 2011). As a result, customers will start purchasing goods from those firms who are involved in the process of environmental sustainability, thereby increasing the market share of the firm (Zhu & Sarkis, 2007).

2.2. Commitment to Sustainable Reverse Logistics:

When it comes to sustainability, resource commitment and reverse logistics are key components for achieving successful SCM. Reverse logistics involves the management of products, components, and materials from the time that they are received until they are returned to a manufacturer, reused, recycled, or disposed of in a safe and ecologically responsible manner (Grant, 2013). Reverse logistics activities can be broken into includes remanufacturing, redesigning, re-hauling, returning, and recalling, refurbishing and repackaging (Rogers et al., 2002).

The success of reverse logistical activities has a direct impact on the firm's competitive advantages in the marketplace (Lehtinen and Ahola, 2010). Therefore, it is important for the organization to understand the cost, considerations, and challenges of engaging in reverse logistics. Furthermore, understanding how reverse logistics can drive sustainability throughout the supply chain can help the organization to optimize and manage their resources more efficiently (Ramirez, 2012).

Research has examined the various elements that have an affect on reverse logistic operations. The financial factor has been a key one, with returns typically ranging from 5-20 percent (Daugherty et al., 2001). A further factor is understanding the consumer needs, especially where online shopping is concerned, and the return policies that are in place (Hazen et al., 2012). Environmental sustainability is another element that needs to be taken into account, as proper disposal and product life-cycles need to be monitored to reduce the impact of post consumption waste on water, landfills, and air (Kasper et al., 2011). Furthermore, there are legal and regulatory implications that need to be considered when implementing reverse logistics, due to the legal requirements for hazardous waste disposal (Ramirez, 2012). Successfully achieving sustainable supply chain management requires the implementation of green purchasing, manufacturing, and packaging standards. Green purchasing involves emphasizing safety certificates and evaluating suppliers based on green criteria. Green manufacturing encourages the recyclability of components and reduced consumption of raw materials and hazardous products. Green packaging involves reusing, reducing the amount of material used, and utilizing renewable and non-hazardous materials (Hsu et al., 2016).

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In conclusion, resource commitment for reverse logistics is paramount to the success of supply chain operations. In order to achieve sustainable goals, firms must take into account the environmental factors, customer needs, and resource commitments. Understanding the cost of engaging in reverse logistics and considering legal and regulatory implications can help the organization optimize their resources and reduce the impact of post consumption waste on the environment.

2.3 Sustainable Reverse Logistic Capabilities:

Sustainable reverse logistics capability is a mechanism that helps firms remain competitive in a rapidly changing market, by providing customers with high levels of service while protecting the environment (Genchev et al., 2010). This means being able to strategize, take action, and adapt to the requirements of customers, partners, and sustainable processes to keep up with customer demands “(Canzaniello et al., 2017; Busse and Mollenkopf, 2017; Normann et al., 2017; Timmer and Kaufmann, 2017)”. By doing so, firms are able to reduce costs, attain a competitive edge, reach heightened customer satisfaction, integrate new technologies, and increase profits (Jack et al., 2010).. There are three theoretical aspects of firm factor, supply chain factor, and institutional factor that constitute the reverse logistic capabilities. The strategy of joint reverse logistic, third-party reverse logistic, and manufacturing reverse logistic are important factors that contribute to the success of reverse logistic capabilities (Vlachos, 2016). However, multiple factors such as lack of technological advancement, poor infrastructure, deficient information flow systems, absence of knowledge of reverse logistic concept and its implications can act as potential barriers in transferring the forward logistic into reverse logistic (Dowlatshahi, 2000).

Organizations that have successfully implemented reverse logistic capabilities have witnessed an increased customer satisfaction and convenience competitive advantages. To accomplish this, researching and assessing the economic value of one’s logistic capabilities towards customers, continuously working towards the improvement of its reverse logistic capabilities, and using reverse logistic benefits for the purpose of marketing, promotions, and expansion, etc. are the vital factors (Pollock, 2007). Organizations are increasingly incorporating the tactic of remanufacturing, rehauling, and recycling of the products instead of procuring new raw materials to reduce their carbon footprint and costs (Partridge, 2010). An example of this is electronic trader, Best Buy, which developed a plan for its repair or rehaul parts reverse logistics. The use of technology in such packages helps operators to identify the working state of the product and determine if the product is eligible for a remanufacturing process or not. This has helped them reduce the costs of transportation every year.

To conclude, reverse logistic capabilities are of pivotal importance for organizations that want to take advantage of its opportunities and create competitive advantages. For this, firms must recognize and encourage the economic value of its capabilities, continuously strive to improve the capabilities for better customer service, and use the benefits as a competitive advantage.

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2.3. Operational Performance:

According to Heizer et al. (2008), the operational performance of a company is measured by its ability to manage its manufacturing lead time, fixed factory overhead costs, and time taken to complete orders. This provides an opportunity for the organization to practice its sustainable reverse logistic activities in order to track and assess the effectiveness of the supply chain operations.

Chen et al. (2004) and Flynn et al. (2010) suggest that firms involved in supply chain operations are responsive to changes in market demand and customer requirements. Tan et al. (1998) found that firms usually set short-term objectives such as minimizing inventory and reducing lead time to improve throughput, with long-term goals of increasing profit and market share. Furthermore, the performance of supply chain management can be measured through operational efficiency and financial outcomes. Operational performance is defined as the capability to effectively utilize resources and assets to produce high quality products with minimum required resources, as well as how quickly the products are delivered (González-Benito, 2007).

Chong et al. (2011) provided an analytical framework which illustrates the relationship between supply chain management practices, innovation within production and service organisations, and the operational performance of the firm. This framework includes customer relationship management (maintaining customer satisfaction), quality of information (minimizing the bullwhip effect), and information technology (ensuring timely delivery, product availability, and accuracy). Furthermore, Kumar and Kushwaha (2018) argued that firms should strive to improve customer relationship management, logistic activities, outsourcing, information sharing, and customer relationship management practices, as this helps to reduce overall costs.

According to Chesaro (2016) there is a positive correlation between the implementation of these practices and improved operational performance of a firm. In addition, while practices such as supplier relationship management, logistic activities, and customer relationship management have a direct impact on operational performance, certain practices such as information sharing and outsourcing can also help reduce the overall expenditure on the supply chain, thereby increasing the profitability and market share of the firm.

In conclusion, operational performance is an important factor for ensuring successful production activities resulting in higher sales and greater profits. Implementing practices such as customer relationship management, quality information, logistic activities, information sharing and customer relationship management can help to provide this performance by reducing the overall costs while improving responsiveness.

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**2.4. Conceptual Framework:
Figure 1 Conceptual Framework**

2.5. Research Hypothesis:

Four hypotheses have been formulated to assess the relationship between independent and dependent variables, both directly and through mediating variables.

H1. There is a direct connection between commitment to sustainable Supply Chain Management and operational performance.

H2. Sustainable reverse logistics capabilities act as a mediator between commitment to sustainable SCM and operational performance.

H3. There is a direct connection between dedication to sustainable reverse logistics and operational performance.

H4. Sustainable reverse logistics capabilities act as a mediator between dedication to sustainable reverse logistics and operational performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

This quantitative research aims to investigate the relationship between resource commitment (CSCM and CRL) and its effect on operational performance (OP); and the impact of social responsibility labelling (SRLC) and other variables on OP. This study brings about a new perspective by using a different laboratory environment from previous studies and by examining both the direct and mediating effects of CSCM and CRL on OP.

A stratified non-proportionate sample of 224 questionnaires was distributed to the managerial level of petrochemical firms through email, in order to collect primary data on the variables that impact operational performance. The questionnaire contained 24 questions on the topic, with the managerial staff of the industry responsible for making the relevant decisions. A systematic statistical analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS version 24 Process

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Macros in order to analyse the data. Additionally, Cronbach's Alpha and correlation analysis were deployed to observe the connection between the variables and their impacts on one another (Kumar, 2017).

3.1. Research Instrument

Table 1 Summary of Research Instrument

Variable	Authors/Source	Number of Items	Scale
Commitment to Sustainable Supply Chain Management	Rizzo et al., (1970)	06	1= Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neutral 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree
Commitment to Sustainable Reverse Logistic	Daugherty et al., (2001)	04	1= Very Low Level of Commitment 2= Low Level of Commitment 3= Moderate Level of Commitment 4= High Level of Commitment 5= Very High Level of Commitment
Sustainable Reverse Logistic Capabilities	Banerjee, (2002)	08	1= Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neutral 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree
Operational Performance	Zhu et al., (2008)	06	1=Not at All 2=Little Bit 3=To Some Degree 4=Relatively Significant 5=Significant

3. RESULT

3.1. Correlation Analysis:

According to the correlation analysis, a positive and significant relationship has been observed between the variables CSSCM, CSRL, SRLC and OP. All the correlation values exceed the significant value of 0.005, thus proving the existence of a positive correlation in this data set. The strongest correlation was observed between SRLC and OP, at a correlation value of 0.790 which is highest among the others. CSSCM and CSRL also showed positive and significant relationship with OP, with correlation values of 0.726 and 0.727 respectively. The corresponding significance values were 0.000 for all the relationships. Additionally, CSSCM, CSRL and OP were found to have positive and significant relationship with SRLC, all having significance values of 0.000 and correlation values of 0.794, 0.740 and 0.790 respectively.

	SRLC (Pearson Correlation)	SRLC (Sig. (2-tailed))	OP (Pearson Correlation)	OP (Sig. (2-tailed))
CSSCM	.794**	.000	.727**	.000
CSRL	.740**	.000	.726**	.000

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SRCL	.790**	.000	.790**	.000
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3.2. Reliability Test of the Model:

Cronbach's alpha value of 0.952 suggests a high degree of correlation between variables, indicating a high level of internal consistency within the conceptual framework.

3.3. Hypothesis Testing:

3.3.1. Hypothesis # 1 and 2:

“The results of the study showed that a positive relationship exists between CSSCM and OP ($\beta=0.2725$; $p=0.0001$; $t=4.1081$), thus lending support to Hypothesis 1. Furthermore, the results showed that SRLC also mediate the relationship between CSSCM and OP ($\beta=0.4091$; $p=0.0000$; $t=8.8497$), thus providing confirmation of Hypothesis 2”.

Variable	Direct Effect without SRLC	Direct Effect with SRLC
CSSCM to OP	0.2725	0.4659

The influence of Customer Service and (CSSCM) on (OP) is reversed partially owing to (SRLC). The direct effect of CSSCM on OP was calculated at 27.25%, and the indirect effect via SRLC was measured at 46.59%. This was further confirmed by the fact that the p-values for both direct and indirect effects were lower than zero, establishing a significant indirect relationship between CSSCM and OP. Therefore, it can be concluded that SRLC mediates the relationship between CSSCM and OP in a positive direction, although not completely.

3.3.2. Hypothesis # 3 and 4:

Results from the hypothesis test support H3 and H4, confirming the positive relationship between CSRL and OP ($\beta=0.4354$; $p=0.0000$; $t=5.4269$), as well as the relationship between SRLC and OP arbitrated through CSRL ($\beta=0.3960$; $p=0.0000$; $t=9.7094$).

Variable	Direct Effect without SRLC	Direct Effect with SRLC
CSRL to OP	0.4354	0.5767

“The indirect effect of CSRL on Operational Performance (OP) is 57.67% (95 percent confidence interval of 0.4208 to 0.7431), while the direct effect of Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) on OP is 43.54% (95 percent confidence interval of 0.2773 to 0.59235). The p-values for both direct and indirect relationships are also less than 0, suggesting that there is a significant indirect relationship between CSRL and OP. Sustainable Reverse Logistics Capability (SRLC) partly mediates this relationship in a positive direction, although the mediation of SRLC is not 100%”.

4. DISCUSSION

To ensure increased operational performance and cost savings, many firms have implemented the use of Reverse Logistics and Sustainable Supply Chain (SSLSC) in their operations, as highlighted by Morgan et al. (2018). “The objective of this study was to analyze the factors that would determine the capabilities of SSLSC in the Petrochemical Industry of Pakistan. According to a previous study conducted by Morgan et al. (2018), the direct effect of an organization's commitment to SSLSC on its operational performance (OP) was found to be 0.517 with a p-value of 0.001, confirming the original hypothesis as true”. The same

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hypothesis was tested in this study and the effects were determined to be 0.2725 with a p-value of 0.0001, thus confirming the hypothesis as true.

Moreover, Morgan et al. (2018) have also determined a mediating effect of Sustainable Reverse Logistics Capabilities (SRLC) between SSLSC and OP, with an effect of 0.427 and a p-value of 0.01. “The same hypothesis was tested again in this study, and the statistical analysis of collected data determined the effecting value to be 0.4659, with a p-value of less than 0.05, thus proving the hypothesis to be true. Regarding the effect of an organization's commitment to Sustainable Reverse Logistics (CSRL) on its operational performance (OP), a previous study conducted by Morgan et al. (2018) determined a direct effect of 0.240 with a p-value of 0.001, thus confirming the hypothesis as true”. The same hypothesis was tested again in this study, and it was found that the effect was 0.4354 with a p-value of 0.0000, thus proving the hypothesis to be true.

Furthermore, Morgan et al. (2018) have determined the mediating effect of SRLC between CSRL and OP to be unsatisfactory, with an effect of 0.133 and a p-value of 0.173. The present study also tested the same hypothesis by performing statistical analysis on the gathered data, and it was determined that the effect was 0.5767 with a p-value of less than 0.05, thus proving the hypothesis to be true. This difference in the effect as compared to that in the previous study may be attributed to the change in the social lab sample size, geographical location, and other factors of the present study. Therefore, the present study has provided valuable insights on the capabilities of SSLSC in the Petrochemical Industry in Pakistan.

5. CONCLUSION

This research highlights the necessity of SSCM and RL for improved operational performance within the petrochemicals industry in Pakistan. By committing to more sustainable approaches, organizations can protect the environment, save costs, and benefit their reputation in the market. To reach this goal, organizations should take steps to improve their sustainable reverse logistics capabilities. This includes introducing sustainable practices and incorporating environmental sustainability into their decision-making processes. Additionally, organizations should create efficient processes to track and manage the supply chain, develop strategic partnerships with suppliers, and review their current supply chain infrastructure. By doing so, these organizations can ensure their success in the market and ensure a more sustainable future in terms of environmental and financial sustainability.

- Involving the employees of the organization in initiatives related to sustainable supply chain and sustainable reverse logistics.
- Providing adequate training opportunities for employees to manage these initiatives.
- Ensuring that the objectives of these activities are clear and transparent to the employees. That these will be beneficial for the environment, the firm and the employees, and that senior management offers their full support.

The limitations of this study are that it is restricted to the city of Karachi and has investigated only one major petrochemical industry (a single social lab). Technological constraints have also impacted the results, as many participants were unfamiliar with the terminology used in the questionnaire, as well as with how to properly fill it out.

In light of the current body of knowledge generated by the study, further investigations can

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explore the following areas:

- Detailed analysis of sustainable supply chain and sustainable reverse logistics is required, to identify necessary changes.
- Research should be conducted in different geographical locations, in order to gain better understanding of processes and initiatives.
- Similar research should be conducted in other social labs apart from petrochemical industry, to explore functioning of supply chain and reverse logistics, and boost organizational performance.

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